

E4.1: Design of Operational Components and Toolkit for Smart Contracts Enabled Negotiation v1.0

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Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business to business
B2C	Business to consumer
BSS	Business Support Systems
CICD	Continuous Integration & Continuous Delivery
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
K8s	Kubernetes
LCM	Lifecycle Management
NS	Network Service
SC	Smart Contract
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
T&C	Terms and conditions
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtualised Network Function
VSC	Vertical Service Consumer
VSP	Vertical Service Provider
VSV	Vertical Service Vendor
xNF	Any Network Functions
ZSM	Zero-touch Network & Service Management

Executive Summary

The convergence of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) and Smart Contracts (SCs) have the potential to generate a cutting-edge digital, decentralized marketplace fostering innovation and collaboration. The 6GENABLERS-DLT project aims to implement a marketplace for the telco industry which embodies agility, transparency, security and efficiency. In this context, the present document describes the design of a key system of the Marketplace, named Smart Contract System. The Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC), which is a sub-component of this system, will provide an entry point to the participating stakeholders to offer, acquire and deploy telco resources and services in an easy way. The document covers the technologies used, the system's operational components and overall design of the informational models. In practice, the SCSC will be used in the project to compose a complete agreement to flexibly represent a series of transactions of telco services for a multi-party, real-time holographic communications application between remote users. The SCSC will then reflect in the DLT the different resources and services exchanged in the agreement, their corresponding offers, orders and instantiations requests using the APIs (Application Programming Interface) offered by the DLT layer.

The main expected outcomes of this document are:

- Complete definition of the SCSC System, as the combination of a Cloud Native (CN) component and a development toolkit component, the related data models, inputs and outputs, that it relies on to represent an agreement for the commercialization of telco services.
- Architecture of the implemented solution introducing its relationship with the rest of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace Platform and detailing the description of the internal functional components and design patterns considered.
- Understanding of the applicability to the project's reference Use Case (UC) by detailing the operational workflows in the corresponding scenarios.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

Taking as input the description of the technologies, specifications, requirements, and capabilities related to Smart Contracts (SCs) in general from E2.1, the present deliverable aims to produce the design report of the SCSC System that will be developed under the project.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

E4.1 is the first release of the results of A4.1 and A4.2 which both primarily take the outcomes from A2.3. Any update to the SCSC System design will be provided along with the description of the first release of the prototype as part of E4.2.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several Chapters that describe the design of the SCSC from different perspectives. Preceding the Chapters, it includes the list of figures, tables and acronyms used throughout the document, and an executive summary of the deliverable. References used for further research of the reader are kept at the end of the document.

- Chapter 1 (this chapter) highlights task commitment and mapping on the work performed with the rest of the project.
- Chapters 2 and 3 provide the overview of the SCSC as a system to fully understand the definition and objectives that are driving the implementation of the system. Since the SCSC is a data-driven system, all the required input and output data models are documented here to further clarify the scope and possibilities of the SCSC.
- Chapter 4 goes into the technical details of the design methodology implemented and the resulting system, which includes the architecture and interfaces.
- Chapter 5 details the applicability and expected operational workflows for the UC scenarios that will be covered by the SCSC implementation.
- Chapter 6 concludes the result of the document with the conclusion analysis.

2 Smart Contract State Composer System Overview

2.1 System Definition and Objective

The SCSC is a key system for the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, its architecture and sub-components are defined in Chapter 4. It enables the interaction with the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) in a programmatically way and represents the entry point for the stakeholders to offer their own resources and services (assets) as well as to visualize what offers are available from other participants, place orders for them and request their deployment. The SCSC is to be complemented with additional components of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, more concretely, the DLT layer will implement the APIs for the SCSC to interact with the SC Codes, which were defined in E2.1 [1] and that will also be provided as part of the DLT layer as ChainCodes [1]. It will additionally leverage the Smart Discovery system (SD) to improve the user experience when searching through available offers by using an intent-based filtering. Lastly, it will listen to alarms and events raised by systems orchestrating and monitoring the deployment of the assets to reflect them in the corresponding DLT transaction and potentially modify the availability of an onboarded asset to alert sellers and buyers.

The SCSC system is built on top of the experience from previous EU projects [2], adding improvements, removing limitations, and ensuring alignment with the newest versions of the most relevant standardization organizations within the telco industry. Its design is the result of the combination of TMForum, ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) PDL, ETSI NFV, and ETSI NFV-EVE [3] [4] [5] [6]. Because the produced specifications by these organizations are wide and flexible to allow different approaches based on the same Information Model (IM), a major part of the design effort of the SCSC relates to structuring and documenting the required data models, which fields are the most important and what is the expected content so that the SCSC and the rest of the Marketplace is able to fully automatize the lifecycle of a telco transaction. Thus, the primary goal of the SCSC is to accurately represent the telco services as objects in the DLT, ensuring a high degree of flexibility, granularity, reusability, and customization possibilities. All models, input and output from the perspective of the SCSC are detailed in the next chapter of the document.

The SCSC will be triggered by the needs of the UC scenarios, which is covered in Chapter 5. It will extract the required elements from the input models and perform any verification needed for those that are critical for the correct functioning of the SCSC and the successive systems in the Marketplace. During ordering time, an initial output will be given in the form of a SC report in a human-readable document to be confirmed by the buyer.

In order to achieve its objective, the SCSC provides the following functionalities:

- Defines the models (based on TMForum) used, how to fill them and ensure that the resource and services offered are mapped in a trustworthy and unique way to the actual telco services so that it is possible to validate the accuracy of the instantiated order respect to what was agreed in the transaction. E.g., enable a way to ensure that the

software of a xNF has not been altered respect to what is specified in the transaction by including a digest or similar verification of the digital content of all software components of the xNF into the corresponding model.

- Enables a way for the stakeholders to interact with the Marketplace to add/consume resources and services. It defines the most appropriate chain of models and workflows to create transactions of telco services following a B2B and B2C business approach. The SCSC is not only in charge of the creation of the SC State for each instantiation of an order, but also of inserting the involved resources, services and offers in the right format into the DLT so that there is a logical link between one object and another.
- Implements a template rendering service for documents to programmatically create a human-readable SC report document including the most relevant fields of the chain of models in the transaction. This is particularly relevant from an auditing point of view.
- It serves as single entry-point to request CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations over the transactions in the DLT for offers, orders and SC States based on the stakeholder inputs and events received from the Marketplace and orchestration layer.

2.2 Smart Contract State Definition

TMForum models are highly flexible and can represent almost the complete lifecycle of a transaction. However, it is limited to the scope of a marketplace and mostly, events that have monetary information. In contrast, in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, apart from the Service Level Agreement (SLA) registration and violation, which are available as TMForum models, there is interest in other Life Cycle Management (LCM) events associated with a particular xNF instance associated to an order since their instantiation and overall control is out of the scope of the Marketplace, meaning that the orchestrating system in charge could take decisions that could lead to a violation of the agreement.

While SLA violations can be calculated outside of the SC Code running in the DLT, in fact, the 6GENABLERS-DLT project will provide a system that proactively monitors the SLA compliance from outside the DLT and informs of violations to the SCSC. The work in [4] and [7] proposes that it is best if the evaluation of LCM events are performed as part of the SC Code for the case of xNFs with the help of an xNF Event Exposure System [1] which pushes LCM events from the Zero-touch network & Service Management (ZSM) framework and the xNF instance.

The output of the SCSC is referred to as the SC State which is further described as the output data model in Chapter 3 and represents the top-most model that will be stored in the DLT linking an instantiation of an order with the relevant events that are associated with it. It will contain the necessary references to obtain the order and offers involved, even in case of bundled orders, which in turn will contain the references to the relevant offers, services and resources, all of these models are described as part of the input data models in Chapter 3. Additionally, it will contain a history of the relevant events which are associated to the order:

- Instantiation requests: This step is outside the scope of TMForum and involves the actual execution of the agreement by the Network Operator or Infrastructure Provider; instantiating a xNF in a ZSM framework, activating slices, providing access to compute resources etc.

- Usage violations: Based on the SLA and Terms and conditions (T&C) specified in the offering, the LCM events from the ZSM framework and the xNF instance could result in a violation of the agreement, such as SLA violation, exceeding the number of instantiations due to scaling actions or manual instantiation of a licensed xNF, expiration of licenses without proactive renewal of the agreement, etc.

3 Data Models

The SCSC is designed around the TMForum specifications models which are truly open and flexible as a way to promote and guarantee the support of a wide range of assets that could be added to the Marketplace. As such, the TMForum data models from this chapter are kept unmodified and could be extended if a new need is discovered. Only for the SC State it has been decided to create custom data models because they are not part of any TMForum specification.

It is worth mentioning that the current design document, and thus the data models shown here, emphasises on the UC scenario presented in E2.1 [1], in which the focus is on the transaction of Network Services (NSs) and Virtualised Network Functions (VNFs), often referred as xNF. For that, the description of the fields of each model and the following chapters will be described keeping in mind the UC scenarios selected for the SCSC. However, the models are open to be used in other scenarios and are not limited to the SCSC UC scenarios and there has already been feedback from the rest of the developments from 6GENABLERS-DLT.

The commitment of this chapter is to select and define the data models focusing on the minimum set of keys, along with their objective and relationship with the UC scenario, which have been identified as needed by systems performing actions over the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. Three different groups of actions have been identified as needed when evaluating the systems developed and how stakeholders would interact with the Marketplace. The first group of actions focus on the process needed to onboard an asset into the marketplace (supply side of the Marketplace). The second relates to the process of acquiring the rights to use the asset (demand side of the Marketplace). The last one relates to the process of consuming/instantiating the acquired asset (deployment side of the Marketplace).

Following the strategy of TMForum, there will be a hierarchy of models linked using references to correctly describe what is being included in the Marketplace in a very granular way that ensures reusability and ease of use. This relationship is included to Figure 3-1 from the supply perspective of the Marketplace, in Figure 3-2 from the perspective of the demand and finally in Figure 3-3 from the deployment perspective. All of these figures provide a high-level view of the models which are later described in sections 3.1 and 3.2. For all three figures, blue is used for those models directly taken from the TMForum specification, and orange is used for those custom models that have been defined as part of the SCSC design.

It is worth mentioning that, although the SCSC defines the data models and will provide a development toolkit to ease their composition, the systems in charge of storing them into the DLT layer and to push the events that need to be reflected in the data model are documented as part of E3.1 [8] and E5.1 [9] and do not necessary follow the same TMForum granular implementation of the data models. They will define the API and the final transaction object that is stored in the DLT. One of the effects of this is that storage will be limited to the parent data models shown in Figure 3-1 to Figure 3-3, and thus, references to external models will be replaced with the actual contents that would be found when accessing the external model. It means that the DLT APIs and storage will be configured to work with All In One (AIO) objects. Figure 3-1 shows one of these AIO objects (ProductOffering), Figure 3-2 shows another AIO object (ProductOrder) and

Figure 3-3 shows the last AIO object (SC State). This mapping and further justification is part of the E3.1 [8].

The aforementioned figures show what references will be replaced with the content as a way to better understand how to navigate the responses from the DLT. The original approach of using references will only be kept for those parent models that will be individually stored in the DLT, they are all marked with “Ref to DLT” in the figures. Any potential update will be documented as part of E4.2 and E4.3.

Figure 3-1 – Supply models tree

Figure 3-2 – Demand models tree

Figure 3-3 – Deployment models tree

3.1 Input Data Models

Figure 3-1 showcases the models that are required to onboard an asset (described as a product) into the Marketplace. They could describe the wide variety of telco assets that may be added to the Marketplace, such as Vertical Services (VS) with NS and VNFs, raw compute and storage capabilities, radio spectrum, edge infrastructure, etc. Each of these assets are exposed to customers with a specific business strategy (described as the combination of an offering, a pricing, agreement, licensing and SLA) as described in E2.1 [1].

Exposing an asset to customer requires three main elements according to TMForum definitions and adopters [10] [11]:

1. A resource specification represents the logical or physical element within the company's inventory or infrastructure that is to be offered.
2. A service specification is built-up from one or more resource specifications and represents the layer of the asset that can be deployed/instantiated.
3. A product specification is the customer-facing part of the asset in the marketplace which is built as the collection of resources and services.

As described in the E2.1, deliverable dealing with UCs and requirements elicitation [1], there are two sequential scenarios planned to highlight the capabilities of the SCSC, one in which a VNF is first purchased by a VSP from a VSV (in a B2B transaction), and then the VSP packages that VNF within a NS and creates a series of offers with different conditions and prices for a VSC to purchase (in a B2C transaction).

From the inventory perspective, both VNF and NS are equivalent as they are packaged in a logical SW artifact (in our case an OSM-compliant tar.gz package) containing a descriptor file and potentially other configuration files. However, from the telco's orchestration perspective, a VNF is different to a NS in the sense that it cannot be instantiated on its own. Although in fact, the NS is simply an abstraction layer that enables a way to connect multiple VNFs and thus, metrics and other LCM actions are done at the VNF level since it is the one that contains the SW that is deployed.

Figure 3-1 showcases the final decision of the SCSC in how to organize this. Both artifacts will be mapped to a resource specification to represent the logical element that is exchanged in the transaction and that will contain any configuration and monitoring scripts required. Then, the VNF resource specification will be directly mapped to a product specification that will be the target of the offering selected in the B2B scenario while the NS will additionally have a service specification which will indicate to customers that it is a ready-to-use asset that can be instantiated and thus it will be the one that will be the target of the offering selected in the B2C transaction.

One of the innovations of the scenarios planned for the SCSC aims to improve the experience from previous projects [2] in the context of enabling a way to use previously ordered assets to compose a complex new offering. This corresponds to mapping the order of the B2B transaction in the B2C offering and ensuring that both offerings are correctly linked.

From a practical perspective, the developed SCSC system will test that an instantiation is requested for a B2C order (between VSC and VSP) and will trigger the creation of two SC states:

- 1- The first SC state shall keep track of the transaction between VSC and VSP and that focuses on the NS and any additional VNF from the VSP included as part of the B2C offering for metrics and pricing.
- 2- The second SC state shall keep track of the transaction between the VSP and the VSV that focuses on the VNF that is internally used by the NS and that was included in the B2B offering.

Although TMForum allows an easy way to bundle offerings together, there is no way to indicate that the bundled offering already has a valid order placed previously. In order to overcome this, the NS product offering will include a SCSC-controlled field in the "prodSpecCharValueUse" key named "relatedOrder" which will contain the ref to an order

in the DLT so that the instantiation of the NS can automatically trigger the creation of the SC states for both orders.

For all models described here, only the most relevant fields and descriptions will be provided for those that have been taken from the TMForum specification. The official documentation is available online and shall be consulted in case of doubt [12].

3.1.1 Service Specification

A service specification in Table 3-1 is used to indicate to the customer that it is a deployable asset. The model itself is just a wrapper to link to resource specifications where the actual logical or physical elements are defined.

Table 3-1 – Service Specification Model

Field	Description	Type
resourceSpecification	Resource specifications	List of resourceSpecifications

3.1.2 Resource Specification

A resource specification in Table 3-2 is the model that enables a way to map logical or physical elements to a model in the TMForum specifications.

Table 3-2 – Resource Specification Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
Attachment	Used to define payment, monitoring and pricing scripts. Located here to expressly specify the price and characteristics of the resource	List of Attachments
resourceSpecCharacteristic	This list includes characteristics referring to the resource to be defined by the provider.	List of ResourceSpecificationCharacteristic [13]
relatedParty	Provider of the resource specification. This list of providers is included here in case the providers of the resource are different than the providers of the containing offer.	relatedParty [14]
lifecycleStatus	Describes if the Marketplace has confirmed its status as unavailable or available	String

3.1.3 Attachment

The attachment model in Table 3-3 is an official TMForum data model which its intended use will be extended. It will be used to host the digital content of small files, such as the legal prose template, the licensing, pricing and payment scripts and the resulting PDF report of the legal prose template after rendering, but also as a content digest for those artifacts that are hosted outside of the scope of the Marketplace, such as the VNF and NS package.

Table 3-3 – Attachment Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
contentType	This field indicates the mimeType format of the attached item.	String
content	This field contains the content itself in base64 format.	Content [15]
Size	This field indicates the exact size of the attached item.	Quantity [16]

3.1.4 Product Specification

A product specification in Table 3-4 is a detailed description of a tangible or intangible object that has been made externally available to consumers through a product offering. This model is of special importance, since it links directly to the resource and service specifications, where NS and VNFs are directly defined.

Table 3-4 – Product Specification

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
serviceSpecification	List of service specifications that belong to this product specification.	List of service specifications
resourceSpecification	List of resources specifications that belong to this product specification.	List of resource specifications

3.1.5 Product Offering

The product offering model in Table 3-5 represents an offer that is available in the catalogue for purchase. In the UC scenario, it is expected that the same product is offered with different pricing mechanisms, payment plans and performance requirements.

Table 3-5 – Product Offering Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Id	DID from the DLT	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
Version	Version of the attachment	String
Agreement	This field includes a legal prose template that will be eventually filled out to generate the final report document linked to the SC State during ordering time.	List of attachments
Category	The categories of the offerings are used for organizing and filtering. It will indicate if it is a B2B or B2C offering, if it relates to network, radio, application, infrastructure ...	List of Strings
Place	Optional location where the offering is available.	Place [25]
productOfferingPrice	This field includes the product offering price model, where the pricing and charging information is defined.	List of productOfferingPrice
productSpecification	Specific product that this offer references.	ProductSpecification
serviceLevelAgreement	Reference to an SLA.	String
validFor	Period of time in which this offer is available.	TimePeriod [17]

prodSpecCharValueUse	This field includes will include elements that from attachments such as license and pricing model names. It is also where, the connection from an offering and a previously bought order will be indicated for reference to the orchestration layers, called “relatedOrders”.	List of ProductSpecificationCharacteristicValueUse [18]
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3.1.6 Product Offering Price

A product offering price in Table 3-6 is based on both, the cost of obtaining a product and the charging policies afterwards. This model, through the pricing algorithm, will define the way in which the VSV or VSP obtain profit from the sale or rental of this product. In addition, the frequency in which payments must be made is defined.

Table 3-6 – Product Offering Price Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
Price	Cost of purchasing the offering.	Money [19]
priceType	Description of the purchasing cost. Single, Recurring, Subscription.	String
pricingLogicAlgorithm	This field includes a link (in the plaSpecId key) to the attachment that describes the payment model based on the usage after the purchasing cost. The attachment is found at the resource attachments key.	List of PricingLogicAlgorithm [20]

recurringChargePeriodLength	Period in which the pricing logic and potentially the purchasing cost should be transferred to the seller.	Integer
recurringChargePeriodType	Type of period, for example, week, month, year... Combines with the previous field.	String
prodSpecCharValueUse	This field will include an element in text format indicating the chosen Pricing Model.	List of ProductSpecificationCharacteristicValueUse [18]

3.1.7 Product Offering Violation

The product offering violation in Table 3-7 is a custom model where violations of a product offering are reflected, similar to SLAViolation but related to the restrictions on the use rather than the performance.

Table 3-7 – Product Offering Violation Model

Field	Description	Type
productOffering	This field references the product offering in the DLT.	String
Violations	This field contains the list of violations of the conditions of the product offering expressed in the same way as SLAs	List of Violation [21]
relatedParty	All parties engaged in the transaction.	List of relatedParty [14]

3.1.8 Life Cycle Management Event

The LCM event in Table 3-8 is a custom model that will be used to reflect events coming from other systems in the Marketplace into the SC State so that the stakeholders are aware of when their instantiation request was finished, if the SLA was correctly configured and any other additional LCM event.

Table 3-8 – Life Cycle Management Event Model

Field	Description	Type
topic	Indicates where the message was sent in the data bus as a way to understand its meaning.	String
event	The model is merely informative and open. It shall not involve any action from additional systems	List of strings

3.1.9 Service Level Agreement

The SLA model in Table 3-9 describes the performance compromises and actions to take when broken. It is part of the product offering but, since it is linked to specific systems in the marketplace, it will be stored independently.

Table 3-9 – Service Level Agreement Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Id	DID from the DLT	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
validityPeriod	The same SLA might apply to multiple offerings and thus the SLA might have a different validity period in the Marketplace.	TimePeriod [17]
Rule	Field used to define the SLA parameters, metrics and thresholds.	List of rules [22]
relatedParty	Parties engaged in the SLA.	List of relatedParty [14]

3.1.10 Service Level Agreement Violation

The SLA Violation model in Table 3-10 maps the SLA rules defined before instantiation with the actual metrics obtained from the performance monitoring of an instantiation.

Table 3-10 – Service Level Agreement Violation Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Description	Description exposed to consumer	String
SLA	SLA Reference in the DLT	String
relatedParty	Parties engaged in the SLA.	List of RelatedParty [14]

Violation	A discrepancy identified by applying rules to Service Level Agreement related entities. This list also includes a subfield to specify what consequence the rule violation should trigger.	List of Violation [21]
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3.1.11 Product Order

The product order model in Table 3-11 is used to purchase one or more offerings. For example, this model will be used in the purchase of a VNF by a VSP from a VSV or when a VSC wants to buy the NS from the VSP. Once the order is accepted, a SC State will be created, enabling a way to request the instantiation for those offerings which its category allow it.

Table 3-11 – Product Order Model

Field	Description	Type
Name	Name exposed to consumer	String
Id	DID from the DLT	String
orderDate	Date and time the order was created.	DateTime [23]
completionDate	Date and time the order was completed.	DateTime [23]
productOrderItem	Each item references to a product offering	List of ProductOrderItem [24]
relatedProductOrderItem	Reference to a previous order in the DLT. Used for the B2C transaction and connected to the offering via relatedOrder product characteristic.	String
state	Shows the lifecycle status of the order based on ProductOrderStateType.	String
Agreement	Contains the rendered legal prose for the order as a human-readable report PDF document in the attachment key of the agreement specification.	Agreement [26]

3.2 Output Data Model

The following set of models will be created directly by the SCSC based on input models and events received from other systems in the Marketplace. Although they do not come directly from the TMForum specifications, they have been designed following a similar approach and it is expected to migrate to TMForum models in the event that they decide to standardize the data models needed to describe the deployment and instantiation of products acquired via the Marketplace.

3.2.1 Event

The Event model in Table 3-12 is a custom model that allows the SCSC State to store monitoring and correction events for the instantiations and violations associated with this product. These events are received from the other systems through the Data Bus.

Table 3-12 – Event Model

Field	Description	Type
eventType	serviveInstantiation, slaInstantiation, offeringViolation, slaViolation, violationCorrection.	String
validFor	When it was first detected (startDateTime) and when it was corrected (endDateTime)	TimePeriod [17]
event	Contains the corresponding event based on the data model described in section 3.1.	Object

3.2.2 Smart Contract State

With each instantiation request, the SCSC will create and store the SC State in Table 3-13. It will enable a way to keep track of what happens after the purchasing of the product to truly offer an E2E telco marketplace.

Table 3-13 – SC State Model

Field	Description	Type
Id	DID from the DLT	String
order	This field includes a reference to the order to which this SC State is related.	String
validFor	Date and time in which the instantiation was requested (startDateTime) and when it was completed (endDateTime)	TimePeriod [17]
events	This list includes all three types of events, instantiations, SLA and offering violations as well as the corrections.	Product events
state	Based on the instantiation status	string
Place	Location where the instantiation was placed	Place [25]

4 Architecture

4.1 Design Principles

State-of-the-art methodologies and tools in the context of SW development, testing and delivery have been selected in this task to contribute to satisfying the quality and trust requirements of the telco marketplace infrastructure created within the project. The use of the methodologies here presented also facilitates the rapid integration of the outcomes in the project allowing faster development iterations based on continuous feedback, which overall leads to an enhanced code quality, achievements of objectives and success rate of the developments.

The SCSC will be implemented keeping in mind the following methodologies:

- Continuous Integration & Continuous Delivery (CICD): The design and development of the SCSC system takes best practices and lessons learnt from CICD, which leads to higher development efficiency, improved code quality, and a more robust and reliable final product.
- Cloud-Native and microservice-based architecture: The system will leverage the tools and capabilities of modern clouds based on Kubernetes (K8s) to optimize the deployment of the microservices of the SCSC. The delivery of the software will be based on Helm to automate and easily manage the K8s resources.
- Stateless: the SCSC does not need to hold any state and needs to have the capability of scaling in events of high demands or even to parallelize multiple transactions.
- Security-by-design: It emphasizes in integrating security measures and considerations throughout the entire software development lifecycle, starting from the initial design phase. In the case of a DLT-based telco marketplace, it is important to account for the security requirements of the interfaces with the DLT layer.

4.2 High-Level Architecture

The 6GENABLERS Marketplace is a multi-system platform that offers complementary functionalities to participating stakeholders. Figure 4-1 depicts the overall Marketplace designed within the project duration. Each system has its own functionalities and will be used for specific purposes directly or indirectly.

Figure 4-1 – 6Genablers general architecture

In the case of the SCSC, it will serve as entry-point to the stakeholders for the functionalities related to the complete catalogue of resources, services and their associated offers, orders and SC states. Chapter 2 has already presented the input data models expected by the SCSC and the description of what each field is used for. Examples of these data models will be provided as part of the SCSC development deliverables, E4.2 and E4.3, to showcase an example for each of the UC scenarios presented in E2.1. The associated operational workflows, including interactions with other components of the Marketplace from Figure 4-1, are included in Chapter 5.

4.3 Low-Level Architecture

The SCSC system will be composed of two main components. One intended to be deployed as part of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace Platform in K8s (right-side component of Figure 4-2), and a second one which will be provided as a Command Line Interface (CLI) distributable, serving as a toolkit to perform common operations required to create the input data models and to interact with the SCSC system (left-side component of the Figure 4-2). Figure 4-2 depicts a lower-level architecture diagram showcasing the functional blocks of each of these two components, which further describe the functionalities covered at design level. Upcoming iterations of the project and integration details between systems might lead to new needs, deliverable E4.2 will contain a more detailed low-level architecture including the set of microservices

developed in the first prototype and how the functional blocks are assigned to each microservice.

Figure 4-2 – Functional Blocks of the SCSC

The SCSC toolkit focuses on functionalities required to correctly fill the input data models that expects the SCSC.

- Digital Content Traceability and Trust: This functionality will enable a way to unequivocally represent a digital asset into the attachment data model from Chapter 3 by applying digital encoding or digesting methods to the content of the asset. Not only will this eliminate the need for external storage systems to host non-standardized data, but it will also increase the level of trust between the parties involved in a transaction. It will effectively turn the DLT into the single source-of-truth of what exactly is part of the transaction and how to audit if there has been any alterations of it throughout the lifecycle of the transaction and its instantiations. Some applicable cases include:
 - o Final SC legal prose report document which combines all the technical and business information from the input data models with the legal prose template to generate a human-readable document in PDF format.
 - o ETSI NFV Artifacts follow a standardized structure containing, in the simplest scenario, a descriptor file describing what the xNF does. These artifacts cannot be directly added as part of the input data models and their delivery to the target infrastructure, onboarding and use is usually completely external to the Marketplace. The objective here is to enable a way to make it possible to verify that the contents of the artifact have not changed from the time when the transaction was made to when the artifact is onboarded into the ZSM ecosystem and then again, each time it is instantiated.
 - o Pricing, licensing and payment logic can only be partially added to the TMForum for very simplistic scenarios. Even in those cases there is still the risk of misinterpretation of the data by the implementing party. By leveraging the proposed approach, the TMForum models will contain a complete description in text and scripting format of what the logic and algorithm should be in each case.
- SC Model Templating and Validation: Although TMForum models are public and can be structured manually, the SCSC dev toolkit will provide a series of

templates for those models strictly necessary for the correct functioning of the SCSC and the Marketplace. Additionally, in the case of the legal prose, the template must follow a specific format for the placeholders that will be taken from other input data models thus, a specific validation will be performed over the models to be added to the Marketplace so that the minimum number of keys and values are present. This block will also be in charge of the encapsulation and extraction of the models into the DLT AIO documents.

- Legal Prose Rendering: This is where the legal prose template will be analyzed to find the required placeholders and inject the corresponding values. This system will be able to return the report back for a last inspection prior to its inclusion to the appropriate model.

The SCSC as a system deployed along with the rest of the Marketplace, focuses on the communication of the input data models to the DLT layer using the appropriate API and authorization as well as the generation of SC State automatically during ordering time.

- Marketplace Catalogue & Order APIs: The SCSC will provide a REST API for the three main actions over the Marketplace:
 - o Supply: Based on the resources created using the SCSC dev toolkit or those already available in the Marketplace, the SCSC will be the component that interacts with the DLT layer to request its storage.
 - o Demand: For those stakeholders seeking to obtain a service or resource offered by someone else, the SCSC will interact with the DLT to consult the catalogue for offers available to create an order later on.
 - o Deployment: Once an order has been included and accepted, the buyer may want to request its usage. This interaction is out of the scope of TMForum and will be reflected as an update to the SC State associated to the order to keep track of all the instantiation requests and events coming from sources outside of the Marketplace such as the ZSM framework.
- SC Models LCM: This block acts as the manager of the SCSC system and will be the one in charge of creating the SC State during ordering time and choosing the correct operation based on the contents of input data and the DLT for the case of the SC State and all of the linked data models. This component will react to events received from the Data Bus of the Marketplace which may include relevant events to be added to the SC State or even alerts that impact on the availability of some models.
- DLT Authorized Adaptation Layer: Although the identity management of the platform is part of the DLT layer directly, the SCSC will be interacting with the DLT in the name of a stakeholder and thus it will need to make sure that the DLT APIs are correctly chosen and authorized based on the role of the stakeholder using the SCSC at each moment and which of the three possible actions (supply, demand, deployment).

4.4 Interfaces

The SCSC is to be integrated with several components of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace for different purposes. Figure 4-3 depicts its overall interactions where everything to the left of the SCSC is considered the NBI and the remaining interfaces are considered as part of the SBI.

Figure 4-3 – SCSC Interactions and Communication

For the most part, the interactions of the SCSC with other components happen synchronously (green arrows in Figure 4-3), however, for those cases in which multiple requests and long-running processes are required in a sequential way, asynchronous communications channels (blue arrows in Figure 4-3) will be used thanks to the integration with the local Data Bus (defined in E3.1 [8]) which will offer a way to send events among systems of the same marketplace instance.

From the point of view of the stakeholders, this will mean that, for instance when they request the onboarding of a new product offering into the Marketplace, it will be marked as “inactive” in the state field. It will only be marked as “active” when an event coming from the Broker is received confirming that all resource specifications are indeed available in the telco infrastructure, xNF artifact exists and matches description, offered resource (e.g., GPU) exists, etc. This workflow is further defined in Chapter 5 and will be also part of P3 and P5 deliverables.

4.4.1 Dev Toolkit Commands

Apart from the interfaces of the SCSC as a system deployed in a K8s cluster, stakeholders will also leverage functionalities offered by the SCSC Dev Toolkit which will be offered in the way of a CLI. **Error! Reference source not found.** describes the most relevant commands that will be created.

Table 4-1 – SCSC Dev Toolkit commands

Command	Input	Output	Description
Create {model}	None	Model template as a local JSON file	Generate a template of a model (AIO document) containing all the necessary placeholders and default values.
Validate	Path to file	Message error in stdout	Raised if any required field is missing, syntax is incorrect or value to a standardized field is not recognized.
Encode	Path to file	Base64 representation of the file	Used to fill attachment models.
Digest	Path to file	Content digest of the file	SHA-256 content digest of a file to be used as a cryptographic representation of the file
Render	Path to file	PDF representation of a legal prose template after populating the placeholders	The command will require to have local access to all external files that have to be used to extract placeholder's values.

4.4.2 North Bound Interface

The NBI of the SCSC will consist of a REST API described following the OpenAPI v2.0 specification and served as a web service that can be consumed directly from the browser.

The API will be organized in three tags aligned with Figure 4-2:

- Supply: Endpoints grouped under this tag will offer a way to onboard each of the input models described in Section 3.1 into the Marketplace. Table 4-2 describes the operations that will be enabled in this case.
- Demand: Endpoints grouped under this tag will offer a way to consult what is available in the Marketplace to be ordered and thus gain access to them to request their deployment. Table 4-3 describes the operations that will be enabled in this case.
- Deployment: Endpoints grouped under this tag will offer a way to consume previously ordered items from the Marketplace by requesting their instantiation. Table 4-4 describes the operations that will be enabled in this case.

Upon request to any of the provided endpoints, the SCSC will respond with an optional output and one of the following HTTP response codes:

- 200: The request was processed.
- 400: The request was incorrect in some way, e.g., method used, param format.
- 500: The request was not processed due to an internal error.

Table 4-2 describes the operations that will be enabled only for AIO documents from Figure 3-1 under the supply tag. The endpoint will be named using “lowerCamelCase” convention applied to the complete name of the model, Product Offering will be under the endpoint “/productOffering” and SLA will be under “/serviceLevelAgreement”

Table 4-2 – Supply endpoints of the SCSC

Operation name: /{model}			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	List of Items of the model	List	List of all items of the given model already onboarded.
Notes			
-			
Operation name: /{model}{did}			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	String uniquely mapping to the model in the DLT.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	JSON	JSON	Single JSON model requested.
Notes			
-			
Operation name: /{model}			
Description		CREATE (POST)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	File	JSON	Models will be onboarded using a local JSON added as a multipart/form-data param.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	Some models will not be marked as ready until other system in the Marketplace confirms their correctness.
Notes			
-			
Operation name: /{model}{did}			
Description		UPDATE (PUT)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	content	JSON	The JSON content of the corresponding model.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Notes			
Using the POST method to update an existing model may result in duplication.			
Operation name: /{model}{did}			

Description		DELETE (DELETE)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	The DID of the corresponding model to delete.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Notes			
-			

Table 4-3 describes the endpoints grouped under the tag “demand” which has the objective to consult product offerings available to be consumed in the Marketplace and place orders for them. This will be achieved by interacting with the Smart Discovery system. It covers CRUD operations over the Product Order AIO document.

Table 4-3 – Demand endpoints for the SCSC

Operation name: /discover			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	{intent}	JSON	JSON representation of the intent described as documented by the SD system.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	List Product Offerings	List	List of all product offerings matching the intent of the resources.
Notes			
The syntax of the intent will be decided as part of SD system.			
Operation name: /productOrder			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	List Product Orders	List	List of all product orders already placed.
Notes			
Operation name: /productOrder/{did}			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	String uniquely mapping to the model in the DLT.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	JSON Model	JSON	Single JSON model requested.
Notes			
-			
Operation name: /productOrder			
Description		CREATE (POST)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description

	File	JSON	Models will be onboarded using a local JSON added as a multipart/form-data param.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	DID of the processed entry in the DLT.
Notes			
Some models will not be marked as ready until other system in the marketplace confirms their correctness.			
Operation name: /productOrder/{did}			
Description		UPDATE (PUT)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	Content	JSON	The JSON content of the product order.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Notes			
Using the POST method to update an existing model may result in duplication.			
Operation name: /productOrder/{did}			
Description		DELETE (DELETE)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	The DID of the corresponding model to delete.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	-	-	-
Notes			

Table 4-4 describes the endpoints grouped under the deployment tag which are used to interact with SC States to request the instantiation of the corresponding products based on an order DID. Table 4-4 is complemented with those endpoints described in Table 4-5 from Section 4.4.2 where the interactions with the data bus are described. In fact, the NBI will only enable a way to create SC States which will trigger an instantiation of an order. After that, users will not be allowed to perform changes over the SC State, any modification will come as a consequence of a change in an order or an event received from the data bus.

Table 4-4 – Deployment endpoints for the SCSC

Operation name: /smartContractState			
Description		CREATE (POST)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	DID of the Order in the DLT.
	Place	Place	Indicates where the instantiation should take place.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	List of SC States	List	List of SC States that have been created.
Notes			
Instantiation parameters may change to adapt to other systems in the platform. More than one SC State might have been created. If the order does not contain service or resource specifications it will return an error. It is not possible to create an order based on empty content.			

Operation name: <code>/smartContractState/{did}</code>			
Description		READ (GET)	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	DID	String	String uniquely mapping to the model in the DLT.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	SCState	SCState	The smart contract state requested.
Notes			
-			

4.4.3 South Bound Interface

While the NBI of the SCSC describes those operations that are initiated by a human actor in a manual or programmatic way, the SBI of the SCSC describes those interactions that happen automatically as a direct or indirect consequence of the NBI. E.g., calls to the DLT layer through one of its API modules to request an update into the ledger, attend events coming from other components of the Marketplace which will provoke an update to a model in the ledger.

Table 4-5 describes the initial set of endpoints that will be created to subscribe and respond to events raised by other systems in the Marketplace, which will all be channeled through the Data Bus. Both, Table 4-5 and the interfaces towards the DLT will evolve as the other systems are developed and thus, the SBI will be further defined as part of the next deliverable describing the prototype of the SCSC.

Table 4-5 – Confirmations and Events

Endpoint	Event	Reaction	Comments
supplyEvent	A component in the Marketplace has approved or refused the onboarding of a supply model.	Update to the supply model in the DLT.	This may happen when telco capabilities are offered but cannot be found by the Broker.
demandEvent	A component in the Marketplace has approved or refused the onboarding of a demand model..	Update to the demand model in the DLT.	This may happen when some of the fields of the order or SC State are not correct
deploymentEvent	A component in the Marketplace has notified the	Update the SC State model.	This may indicate that a NS and VNF is

	result of the instantiation of the service/resource.		running, which shall be stored as an update to an instantiation event in the SC State.
serviceLevelAgreementEvent	A component in the Marketplace has raised an event regarding the SLA in a particular instantiation from an order.	Update to the SC State model in the DLT	This may indicate that a NS is not meeting SLA, which shall be stored as an SLA event in the SC State
instanceEvent	A component in the marketplace has raised an event regarding the offering agreement in a particular instantiation from an order.	Update to the SC State model model in the DLT	This may indicate that a NS is being used in a way not included in the agreement which shall be stored as an offering event in the SC State

5 Operational Workflows

5.1 UC Scenarios

The SCSC is designed to be flexible and support the exchange of any type of telco service that can be mapped to the input models described in Chapter 3. This could include slices, spectrum, computing resources, etc. The objective of the proposed operational workflows in this Chapter is to showcase the potential of the SCSC taking as basis the reference UC of the project. As introduced in E2.1, it has been planned to evaluate two complementary types of interactions namely, B2B scenario and B2C scenario, in which two actors exchange xNFs.

5.1.1 B2B Scenarios

This first interaction would correspond to a scenario where a Service Provider is interested in integrating their application into a telco infrastructure by leveraging general-purpose, commercial-grade telco xNFs, such as edge caches, video proxies or similar, without having to develop them.

In this case, both actors are providers and there is no direct instantiation of the services involved in the transactions.

5.1.2 B2C Scenarios

This second interaction corresponds to a scenario where the Service Provider wants to offer a way to access the previously bought VNF as well as their own application directly from within the telco infrastructure instead of having users connected to an external service hosted on the public internet.

In this case, one of the actors is directly interested in consuming the services and it should enable them to request an instantiation of the services involved in the transaction.

5.2 Workflows

Below, the workflow diagrams will be presented representing the interactions between the entities in the scenario, depending on whether the transaction is of the B2B or B2C type. A distinction will be made between the creation of an offer and the acquisition of an order, separating these cases into different flows.

As a note for the diagrams, the green arrows indicate synchronous communications, while blue arrows indicate messages that cross the Data Bus. For the later type of communication, the diagrams do not show the interactions with the bus to reduce its size.

5.2.1 B2B Product Offering

When creating a product offering in a B2B scenario, the VSV will begin by composing the required AIO document using the SCSC Dev Toolkit. As seen in Figure 5-1, this will involve the definition of all fields after the Dev Toolkit had created a template based on some input information from the VSV. Then, they will validate the document with the Dev Toolkit prior to accessing the NBI of the SCSC to request its onboarding.

When the product offer is sent to the Offering API, it is checked that the necessary resources associated with that offer are available, through the Broker for Resource Controller. Initially, the resource associated with the product offer has a “unavailable” status. When the SCSC receives the response about the availability of the resources, it updates the status of the resource to “available”. In any case, the offer remains persistent in DLT Trading. This process occurs when publishing any offer, regardless of whether it is a B2B or B2C scenario.

Once this workflow is completed, the result would be a VNF product offer available in the Marketplace and could be consulted by the VSP from their own instance of the Marketplace using the appropriate NBI endpoint.

Figure 5-1 – B2B Product Offering Workflow

5.2.2 B2B Product Order

In this second workflow shown in Figure 5-2, the VSP aims to purchase the product offering that was created by the VSV and that should be available in the Marketplace, specifically the VNF offer seen in the previous subsection. This time, the SCSC enables a way for the VSP to discover relevant product offerings in the Marketplace using the intent-based discovery functionality of the Smart Discovery [9]. Once the desired product offering is found, the VSP will proceed in a very similar way to the VSV. By using the SCSC Dev Toolkit, they will obtain a template of the model where they will need to replace the necessary information, which also includes the inspection of the rendered legal prose template to create and add it to the product order as an attachment to the “agreement” key (see Figure 3-2).

The next steps in Figure 5-2 show how the product order is initially set to active directly as the individual product offerings have already been validated. It will be again during instantiation time when the Marketplace will make sure that the infrastructure is ready, and it may result in a deactivation of the order and offer and the subsequent offering violation. In the particular case of the VNF order, the SCSC will detect that it does not contain a service specification and thus cannot be instantiated. An SC State for this particular order can only be created as an automated reaction to an instantiation of a NS order, which is shown in the last workflow.

Figure 5-2 – B2B Product Order Workflow

5.2.3 B2C Product Offering

This new type of transaction is shown in Figure 5-3, the workflow is symmetric to the one in the B2B product offering with the exception that in this occasion, the product offering will include a service specification, with the help of input information given to the SCSC Dev Toolkit, to denote that the product is deployable. It will also require knowing the order DID returned by the SCSC in the B2B product order workflow to be added to the product offering in the custom key “relatedOrders” of its standard “prodSpecCharValueUse” key.

Figure 5-3 – B2C Product Offering Workflow

5.2.4 B2C Product Order

This workflow, shown in Figure 5-4, is completely symmetric to the one seen in the B2B product offer in Figure 5-2. Just the actor is updated. It is worth noticing how the VSC that places the order for the NS is unaware of the VNF exchanged between the VSV and the VSP. The offering that the VSC has selected has an internal field that links to the VNF order but, since the commercial relationship for the VNF was already established via an order (Figure 5-2) and is exclusively among VSP and VSV, the product order for the NS does not need to include the offering of the VNF.

The instantiation of the NS will trigger the monitoring of the two orders, but that will be shown in Figure 5-5.

Figure 5-4 – B2C Product Order Workflow

5.2.5 B2C Product Order Instantiation

This last workflow shown in Figure 5-5, depicts how an instantiation is requested and its effect on the created SC States from the SCSC perspective.

Figure 5-5 – Instantiation Workflow

6 Conclusion

The present document provides the design report for the Smart Contract System, it contains the definition of the two core developments that will be carried out, the SCSC Development Toolkit and the SCSC module, covering architecture, data models and functionalities. It also includes an initial analysis of its interactions with the rest of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace by describing its interfaces and workflows.

With the help of the SCSC, stakeholders wanting to offer, acquire and consume telco assets from the Marketplace, will be able to simplify the processes by using a single API and reduce the learning curve to interact with the Marketplace by using a Development Toolkit.

The design of the SCSC and the rest of the systems for the Marketplace has already led to improvements in the overall architecture and further definition of the functionalities and requirements from each other. In particular, several integrations have been identified, which may involve the refinement of the interfaces, but it is expected that the integration specifications will become clearer during the next phase of the project in which the prototype for each system will be developed.

Design and development of the SCSC will continue and an update will be reported as part of the E4.2 detailing the prototype implemented.

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[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/Product/ProductSpecificationCharacteristicValueUse.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Product/ProductSpecificationCharacteristicValueUse.schema.json) at
[cf5770b2ecafb2c8ae15a931ae8351fa04db467e](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Product/ProductSpecificationCharacteristicValueUse.schema.json) · [tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model)
- [19] TMForum – Money Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/Common/Money.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Common/Money.schema.json) at
[cf5770b2ecafb2c8ae15a931ae8351fa04db467e](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Common/Money.schema.json) · [tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model)
- [20] TMForum – Pricing Logic Algorithm Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/Product/PricingLogicAlgorithm.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Product/PricingLogicAlgorithm.schema.json) at
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- [21] TMForum – Violation Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/EngagedParty/Violation.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/Violation.schema.json) at
[master · tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/Violation.schema.json)
- [22] TMForum – Rules Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/EngagedParty/Rule.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/Rule.schema.json) at
[cf5770b2ecafb2c8ae15a931ae8351fa04db467e](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/Rule.schema.json) · [tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model)
- [23] ISO – ISO 8601 – Date and time format – [ISO – ISO 8601 — Date and time format](https://www.iso.org/standard/52003.html)
- [24] TMForum – Product Order Item Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/Customer/OrderItem.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Customer/OrderItem.schema.json) at
[master · tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Customer/OrderItem.schema.json)
- [25] TMForum – Place Schema –
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/Common/Place.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Common/Place.schema.json) at
[cf5770b2ecafb2c8ae15a931ae8351fa04db467e](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/Common/Place.schema.json) · [tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model)
- [26] TMForum – Agreement Specification --
[Open_Api_And_Data_Model/schemas/EngagedParty/AgreementSpecification.schema.json](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/AgreementSpecification.schema.json) at
[master · tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model \(github.com\)](https://github.com/tmforum-apis/Open_Api_And_Data_Model/blob/master/schemas/EngagedParty/AgreementSpecification.schema.json)

